

Analytical Method Development and Validation of Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method For Pitolisant Hydrochloride in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To develop and validate a simple, accurate, precise, and stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Pitolisant HCl in bulk and tablet formulations, including stability studies. **Methods:** The chromatographic separation was achieved using a C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) with a mobile phase consisting of Acetonitrile, water and methanol (70:20:10 v/v/v, adjusted with 0.1% Triethylamine) at a flow rate of 1.5 ml/min. Detection was performed at 221 nm with a UV detector. The method was validated as per ICH Q2(R1) guidelines for linearity, precision, accuracy, ruggedness, robustness, LOD, and LOQ. Forced degradation studies were conducted under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic conditions to evaluate the stability-indicating nature of the method. **Results:** Pitolisant showed a sharp and symmetric peak with a retention time of 6.01 minutes. The method was linear in the concentration range of 22.25-111.25 μg/ml with correlation coefficient ($r^2 = 0.9997$). Precision results (%RSD) were below 1.5%, and recovery values ranged from 99.98% to 100.59%, confirming accuracy. LOD and LOQ were found to be 4.8302 μg/ml and 14.63 μg/ml, respectively. while the drug was relatively stable under Oxidation and photolytic, acid, base and reduction studies. Degradation products were well resolved from the main peak, proving the method's stability-indicating capability. **Conclusion:** The developed RP-HPLC method is simple, precise, accurate, and stability-indicating. It is suitable for routine quality control, stability testing, and degradation behaviour studies of Pitolisant HCl in bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

Keywords: Pitolisant, RP-HPLC, Stability studies, Validation, ICH guidelines, Pharmaceutical dosage form.

INTRODUCTION

Pitolisant, a selective histamine H₃ receptor antagonist/inverse agonist, is an innovative therapeutic agent for treating narcolepsy and related disorders of excessive daytime sleepiness. Its mechanism of action involves increasing histaminergic neurotransmission in the central nervous system, promoting wakefulness and reducing sleep attacks. chemical name: 1-[3-[3-(4-chlorophenyl) propoxy] propyl] piperidine. Hydrochloride. The molecular formula of Pitolisant is C₁₇H₂₇Cl₂NO.HCl, and the molecular weight 332.3 g/ml

Pitolisant displays high selectivity for H₃ receptors compared to other histamine receptor subtypes. Pitolisant also modulates acetylcholine, noradrenaline and dopamine release in the brain by increasing the levels of neurotransmitters but does not increase dopamine release in the stratal complex, including the nucleus accumbent. [L1471] At lower nanomolar concentrations, pitolisant acts as an inverse agonist at H₃ receptors and enhances the release of endogenous histamine over the basal level^[1].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Pitolisant HCl

Due to its clinical importance and therapeutic use, the development of accurate, sensitive, and validated analytical methods for the estimation of pitolisant is essential. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) has emerged as a widely accepted technique for drug analysis because of its high resolution, reproducibility, and reliability in Pharmaceutical quality control. Analytical methods also play a crucial role in stability studies, including forced degradation studies, which are recommended by ICH guidelines to evaluate the chemical stability of drug substances under stress conditions. Such studies ensure drug safety, efficacy, and quality throughout its shelf life. Determining the percentage degradation under different stress conditions ensures that the method is stability-indicating and suitable for regulatory applications [5,6]. The present work focuses on the development and validation of a simple, precise, accurate, and stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for the quantitative estimation of Pitolisant in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form, along with stability studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instrumentation

The analysis was performed using a Shimadzu HPLC system equipped with an LC-20AD pump, a UV-Visible detector, and LabSolutions software, utilizing a Phenomenex C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm × 5 μm). An electronic balance (Shimadzu AUX-220) was used for weighing, and sample sonication was carried out using a sonicator. A hot air oven (Infra DIGI, up to 250 °C) and a UV light chamber were employed for stability and forced degradation studies.

Reagents and Chemicals

All chemicals and reagents used were of HPLC grade and obtained from Qualigens India Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai,

India. Pure Pitolisant HCl was supplied by a pharmaceutical company in Telangana, India, while Wakix® tablets (containing 4.45 mg of Pitolisant per tablet as 5 mg Pitolisant HCl) were obtained from a pharmaceutical manufacturer. The solvents and reagents used included HPLC-grade acetonitrile, water, methanol, 0.1% triethylamine (TEA), 0.1 N sulfuric acid, 0.3% hydrogen peroxide, 10% sodium bisulfite, and 0.1 N potassium hydroxide.

METHOD OPTIMIZATION

The chromatographic method was optimized by systematically adjusting parameters such as mobile phase composition, detection wavelength, diluent, and flow rate to obtain sharp, symmetric peaks with suitable retention time and resolution.

Mobile phase Optimization

Different combinations of water, methanol, and acetonitrile, both with and without basic modifiers, were evaluated. Mobile phases without modifiers caused peak broadening and tailing. The addition of 0.1% triethylamine (TEA) significantly improved peak symmetry and reproducibility. The optimized mobile phase consisted of acetonitrile, water, and methanol in a ratio of 70:20:10 v/v/v containing 0.1% TEA, which produced sharp, symmetric peaks with an acceptable retention time.

Selection of Diluent

The optimized mobile phase-Acetonitrile: water: methanol (70:20:10 v/v/v) with 0.1% TEA was chosen as the diluent to ensure complete solubility of the drug, compatibility with the chromatographic system, and reproducible performance.

Selection of Wavelength

The UV spectrum of Pitolisant was scanned over the 200–400 nm range. The drug exhibited maximum absorbance at 221 nm, which was selected as the detection wavelength because it provided maximum sensitivity with minimal baseline noise.

Optimization of Flow Rate

Flow rates between 1.0 and 1.5 ml/min were evaluated. Higher flow rates caused a reduction in resolution, while lower flow rates prolonged analysis

time. A flow rate of 1.5 ml/min was found to provide an optimal balance between resolution and runtime, and was therefore selected for the method.

Final Optimized Condition

The final chromatographic conditions included a Phenomenex C18 column (4.6 × 250 mm), mobile phase Acetonitrile: water: methanol (70:20:10 v/v/v) containing 0.1% TEA, a flow rate of 1.5 ml/min, UV detection at 221 nm, and an injection volume of 20 µL. Under these conditions, the method produced sharp, symmetric peaks with system suitability parameters that met ICH requirements.

Analytical Method Development

Preparation of Mobile Phase

The mobile phase was prepared by mixing Acetonitrile, water, and methanol (70:20:10 v/v/v) with 0.1% TEA, followed by filtration through a 0.45 µm membrane filter and degassing using sonication before use.

Preparation of standard stock solution

An accurately weighed quantity of Pitolisant (44.5 mg) was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in the mobile phase, and diluted to the mark to obtain a stock solution of 4450 µg/ml. From this stock, 1 ml was further diluted to 10 ml in another volumetric flask, resulting in a working solution of 445 µg/ml.

Preparation of sample solution

Twenty tablets were weighed to calculate the average weight and then finely powdered. A portion of the powder equivalent to 4.45 mg of Pitolisant was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask containing 5 ml of the mobile phase, sonicated for 15 minutes, and allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 minutes. The solution was then diluted to the mark with the mobile phase to obtain a sample stock solution of 445 µg/ml, which was filtered through Whatman filter paper. From this stock solution, 1 ml was further diluted to 10 ml with the mobile phase to yield a working sample solution of 44.5 µg/ml.

METHOD VALIDATION

System Suitability

System suitability was evaluated by injecting the standard solution under the optimized chromatographic conditions. Pitolisant produced a sharp, symmetric peak at 6.010 min. The theoretical plates were greater than 2000, and the tailing factor was below 2.0, indicating good column efficiency and peak symmetry. All parameters met the ICH acceptance criteria.

Linearity

Linearity was assessed by preparing standard solutions of Pitolisant in the range of 22.25–111.25 µg/ml. Aliquots of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 ml of the stock solution (445 µg/ml) were each transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks and diluted to volume with the mobile phase. Each solution was injected into the HPLC, and calibration curves were constructed by plotting peak area versus concentration.

Precision

Precision of the method was evaluated by analyzing a sample solution of Pitolisant (44.5 µg/ml) six times within the same day, and the %RSD of peak areas was calculated to assess repeatability.

Accuracy

Accuracy was determined using the standard-addition method at three concentration levels: 50%, 100%, and 150% of the target concentration. Pre-analyzed tablet powder equivalent to 4.45 mg of Pitolisant was spiked with known amounts of the standard drug and analyzed in triplicate.

Robustness

The robustness of the developed HPLC method was evaluated by introducing deliberate, minor variations in chromatographic parameters and examining their effect on system suitability. Each parameter was altered individually, and the sample solution was injected in triplicate for each condition:

1. Mobile Phase Composition: The ratio of Acetonitrile: water: methanol (70:20:10 v/v/v) with 0.1% TEA was varied by ±1.0 ml (69:18:13 and 72:20:8 v/v/v).

- Detection Wavelength: The wavelength was altered by ± 1 nm (220 nm and 222 nm).
- Flow Rate: The flow rate was adjusted by ± 0.1 ml/min (1.4 ml/min and 1.6 ml/min).

For each variation, the %RSD of the mean peak area was calculated. No significant changes were observed in retention time, peak symmetry, or system suitability parameters, confirming that the method is robust.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness was assessed by analyzing a Pitolisant sample solution (44.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) using two different analysts and two different instruments under the same operational and environmental conditions. The results confirmed that the method is reproducible across analysts and instruments.

LOD & LOQ

The Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) were calculated according to ICH guidelines using the standard deviation (σ) of the y-intercept and the slope (s) of the calibration curve:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \frac{\sigma}{s}; \text{LOQ} = 10 \times \frac{\sigma}{s}$$

Where:

- σ = standard deviation of the response
- s = slope of the calibration curve

Forced degradation studies

Stability studies were performed to evaluate the stability of Pitolisant under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, reductive, and photolytic stress conditions. The drug was analysed using the validated RP-HPLC method, and the extent of degradation was quantified as the percentage of drug remaining. Results indicated that Pitolisant is stable under most stress conditions, confirming the stability-indicating capability of the method.

Acid degradation^[7]

A 1 ml aliquot of the 445 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Pitolisant working standard solution was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask, and 1 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ was

added. The mixture was kept for 24 hours, neutralized with 1 ml of 0.1 N KOH, diluted to volume with diluent, and analyzed by HPLC. Chromatograms were recorded to monitor changes during the stress period.

Alkali degradation^[7]

A 1 ml aliquot of the 445 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Pitolisant working solution was treated with 1 ml of 0.1 N KOH and left for 24 hours. The solution was then neutralized with 1 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄, diluted to the mark with diluent, and analysed by HPLC.

Oxidative degradation^[7]

A 1 ml aliquot of the 445 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ working solution was mixed with 1 ml of 0.3% hydrogen peroxide and allowed to stand for 24 hours. The volume was adjusted with diluent, and the solution was analysed by HPLC to monitor oxidative degradation.

Reduction degradation^[8]

A 1 ml aliquot of the 445 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ working solution was treated with 1 ml of 10% sodium bisulfate and kept for 24 hours. The solution was diluted to volume with diluent and analyzed by HPLC

Photolytic degradation^[8]

The raw Pitolisant material was exposed to direct sunlight for 4 hours. A 445 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution was prepared from this material, and 1 ml was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask, diluted to volume with diluent, and analyzed by HPLC to assess photolytic degradation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION

The HPLC procedure was optimized to develop a suitable method for the determination of Pitolisant in tablet dosage form. Initially, different ratios of methanol, acetonitrile, and water were tested as mobile phases. Based on peak shape and resolution, a combination of water and acetonitrile was selected for further optimization that shown in table 2.

TABLE 1: The different ratios of mobile phase tried and remark on obtained peaks

S.No	Mobile phase composition	Flow rate	Interference
1	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (40:30:30 v/v/v)	1 ml/min	No peak detected
2	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (60:25:15 v/v/v)	1 ml/min	No peak detected
3	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (60:25:15 v/v/v)	1 ml/min	No peak detected
4	0.1% OPA with water: acetonitrile: methanol (60:30:10 v/v/v)	1.2ml/min	Retention time is acceptable but peak shows tailing.
5	0.1% OPA with water: acetonitrile: methanol (60:30:10 v/v/v)	1.2ml/min	Peak shows tailing.
6	Acetonitrile: water: methanol (70:20:10 v/v/v) with 0.1% TEA	1 ml/min	Sharp peak with minimal baseline noise
7	Acetonitrile: water: methanol (70:20:10 v/v/v) with 0.1% TEA	1.2 ml/min	Minimal baseline noise
8	Acetonitrile: water: methanol (70:20:10 v/v/v) with 0.1% TEA	1.5ml/min	Peak showed good symmetry and acceptable retention time

The optimized chromatogram for pitolisant is presented in **Figure 2** (blank) and **Figure 3** (optimized chromatogram)

<Peak Table>

FIGURE 3: Optimized chromatogram for Standard**Method Validation**^[9]

The developed HPLC method for Pitolisant was validated as per ICH guidelines.

System suitability

System suitability and chromatographic parameters, including tailing factor and theoretical plates, were evaluated, and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: System suitability parameters of pitolisant

Parameters	Results
Number of theoretical plates or efficacy	17323
Tailing factor	1.472
Retention time	6.010
Peak area	224692

Linearity

The method demonstrated excellent linearity, with the regression equation expressed as $y = mx + c$ and a correlation coefficient of $R^2=0.9997$, confirming its suitability for quantitative analysis. The results are summarized in Table 3. Calibration curves constructed over the concentration range of 6–30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ are shown in Figure 4. The analytical parameters, including the correlation coefficient,

slope, intercept, LOD, and LOQ, are presented in Table 4.

Table 3: Calibration curve data for pitolisant

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak Area
22.25	258702
44.5	510773
66.75	769693
89	998866
111.25	1272128

Figure 4: Calibration curve for pitolisant

Table 4: Optical parameters and linearity data of Pitolisant

Parameters	Pitolisant
Beer's law range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	22.25- 111.25
Regression equation ($y=mx + c$)	$Y = 11352x + 3594.7$
Slope	11352
Intercept	3594.7
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9997
Standard error	6783.93
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	4.8305
Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	14.6381

Precision

System precision was evaluated by performing six replicate injections of Pitolisant (44.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$).

The %RSD of 0.3153% was well within acceptable limits, confirming the precision of the method (Table 5, Figure 5)

Table-5: Precision of Pitolisant Formulation

Precision	Label claim	Amount found	% purity	Average %	S. D	%RSD
1	4.45	4.44	99.77	99.99	0.3153	0.3153
2		4.45	100			
3		4.43	99.55			
4		4.46	100.22			
5		4.47	100.44			
6		4.45	100			

* Mean of 6 Observations

Figure 5: Precision chromatogram for pitolisant**Accuracy**

Accuracy was evaluated by the standard addition method at three concentration levels, each analysed in triplicate. The mean % recovery of pitolisant was within acceptable limits, confirming the accuracy of the proposed method (Table 6).

Table-6: Accuracy (recovery) data for Pitolisant

Sample	% Conc	Sample amount (µg/ml)	Amount spiked (µg/ml)	Estimated amount (µg/ml)	Recovered amount (µg/ml)	Average % Recovery*	SD	%RSD
PITO	50	44.5	22.25	66.89	22.39	100.62	0.9672	0.9615
	100	44.5	44.5	88.99	44.49	99.97	0.7466	0.7467
	150	44.5	66.75	111.21	66.71	99.94	0.8528	0.8521

* Mean of 3 Observations

Robustness

Robustness of the method was evaluated by introducing deliberate variations in flow rate (± 0.1

ml/min), detection wavelength (± 1 nm), and mobile phase composition (± 1 ml). The %RSD values remained within acceptable limits, confirming that the method is robust. The results of the robustness study are presented in Table 7.

Table-7: Robustness data for Pitolisant

PARAMETER	AMOUNT FOUND (mg)	% PURITY	SD	% RSD
FLOW RATE				
1.4 ml/min	4.45	100.14	0.3415	0.3410
1.5 ml/min	4.45	100.16	0.4479	0.4471
1.6 ml/min	4.45	100.07	0.7186	0.7180
WAVELENGTH				
220 nm	4.46	100.22	0.4501	0.4491
221 nm	4.47	100.44	0.5934	0.5908
222 nm	4.45	99.99	0.2215	0.2250
MOBILE PHASE COMPOSITION				
69:18:13 (0.1 %TEA)	4.47	100.4	0.7600	0.7569
70:20:10 (0.1 %TEA)	4.45	99.99	0.2250	0.2250
72:20:8 (0.1 %TEA)	4.46	100.22	0.5915	0.5902

* Mean of 3 Observations

Ruggedness

Ruggedness was assessed under varying conditions, and the %RSD values remained within acceptable

limits, confirming the method's reproducibility. The results are summarized in Table 8.

Table-8: Ruggedness data for Pitolisant

Sample	Concentration (µg/ml)	Condition	% obtained*	S.D	% RSD
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PITO	44.5	Analyst-1	100.4	0.9487	0.9443
		Analyst-2	99.9	0.3036	0.3039
		Instrument-1	100.29	0.7752	0.7735
		Instrument-2	100.23	0.5325	0.5312

* Mean of 6 Observations

Forced degradation studies

Stability studies were performed to assess the behavior of Pitolisant under various stress conditions. The drug remained stable under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, photolytic, and reductive conditions, indicating no significant degradation. These results confirm that the developed RP-HPLC method is stability-indicating and suitable for routine analysis. The findings are summarized in Table 9.

Table-9: Forced degradation data for Pitolisant

Stress conditions	Time interval	% degradation
Acid degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Alkali degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Oxidative degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Reduction degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Photolytic degradation	4 hrs	Not degraded

Figure 6 : Acid degradation chromatogram of Pitolisant

Figure 7: Alkali degradation chromatogram of Pitolisant

Figure 8: oxidation degradation chromatogram of Pitolisant

Figure 9: Reduction degradation chromatogram of Pitolisant

Figure 10: Photolytic degradation chromatogram of Pitolisant

- **Advantages of developed method:**
- **Simplicity** – Employs a straightforward mobile phase (**Acetonitrile: water: methanol with 0.1% TEA**), eliminating the need for complex buffer systems.
- **Sensitivity** – Capable of detecting and quantifying Pitolisant at **low concentrations**, with **LOD and LOQ values** well within acceptable limits.
- **Accuracy and Precision** – Produces highly reproducible results, with **%RSD values** meeting ICH guideline requirements.
- **Stability-Indicating Capability** – Effectively monitors drug degradation under various **stress conditions**, confirming method reliability.
- **Rapid Analysis** – Short **retention time (6.010 min)** allows faster analysis and increased sample throughput.
- **Cost-Effectiveness** – Uses **readily available solvents** (acetonitrile, water, methanol) without the need for expensive buffers or modifiers. Short run times reduce **solvent consumption and instrument usage**, lowering per-sample costs.
- **Versatility** – Suitable for estimation of Pitolisant in both **bulk drug and tablet dosage forms**, making it ideal for routine **quality control**.
- **Robustness and Ruggedness** – Delivers consistent and reliable results despite **minor deliberate changes** in chromatographic

conditions or variation between analysts and instruments

CONCLUSION

A simple, precise, and robust RP-HPLC method was successfully developed and validated for the estimation of Pitolisant in both bulk drug and tablet dosage forms. The optimized chromatographic conditions, employing Acetonitrile: water: methanol (70:20:10, v/v/v) with 0.1% TEA as the mobile phase, produced sharp and symmetric peaks with a retention time of 6.010 min, a flow rate of 1.5 ml/min, and a detection wavelength of 221 nm. The method exhibited excellent linearity over the concentration range of 22.25–111.25 µg/ml, with a correlation coefficient ($R^2=0.9997$). Validation parameters, including system suitability, precision, accuracy, robustness, and ruggedness, were found to be within ICH guideline limits, confirming the reliability of the method. Stability studies demonstrated that Pitolisant remained stable under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, reductive, and photolytic conditions.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All the authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Declared none.

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